

Francis Bacon, Need a man of the world

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ABSTRACT

Francis Bacon is the heart and soul of English Prose. He could transform literature of sense into literature of power. No prose writer in English had a more conspicuous style than Bacon. He embroidered English with the jewels of Latin phrases. His command over English was superfine and even matchless. He had few rivals but no superior in prose rhetoric. His subject is not great but splendid glory. His essays are just attempts and not fully worked out dissertations. They are free from overcrowded imagery and are simple as leaves of glass. But, they light up his thoughts and serve as the sprightly sources of inspiration. Before 1350, there was no prose in the form of a text in English. And Bacon has filled the gap. Alfred, Sailsbury, Wycliff, Trevisa and Mandeville can be listed as the founder of English Prose. Even Bacon is exalted as the Godfather of English prose.

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Introduction

Bacon was born in the domestic noblest family. His father was a lord, keeper of the royal seal. His great grandmother's husband was a minister in the political Queen Elizabeth's. He had been a keen intellectual in his childhood, attracted the queen's attention. His knowledge grew with his studies at Cambridge and later with his law degree. He was elected to parliament and became one of the Queen's counselors in 1598. Next, when James came to the throne, Bacon was promoted to the highest position 1618, in judicial office in the country. Then, Bacon named epithet of Knight and he was elevated into the rank of Viscount of St. Alban's. Then the wheel of fortune began to turn downwards to him in the life. He

was climbing towards the peak, slipped and fell. He was accused to get bribes from the petitioner. He was imprisoned for some years. Later he was rejected from all public and government officials. He died while in the attempting to freeze a chicken for the scientific research.

A Man of Essayist

Francis Bacon is called the father of the English Essayist. He is the first man use the word *essay* in English. His writing style is unique and it made its special to the literary genre for his essays. He called himself born for the common good of the world. His keen pole of magnetic knowledge was pointing in the way of worldly desires. His collection of essays has achieved the immortality of the literary world. It has been compare to the Tamil phrases like Nanneri, Naladhi, and Mudhumozhi Kanchi etc. He has been established himself through of his insightful Tamil writers like Parimelazhagaar and Sena Ghariyar. Not only Bacon not a columnist. He is also a philosopher, scientist and legal expert. The Renaissance movement in England fostered a dynamic nature of multifaceted energy, ambition, and worldly inclination as well as restless contradictions. He is a perfect example of that renaissance period. It is worth considering here that the English poet, Alexander pope said about he is the wisest, the most brilliant, and the most disreputable of mankind.

Eloquent voice of optimism

Bacon has revealed several kinds of writing and excelled in every form. He is the monarch of his own style. His essays are the choicest blend of philosophy, morals and wisdom. They are filled with the civil and moral values. They are a handbook of worldly wisdom. They are polished mirrors that reflect his knowledge of the world. Bacon's Fifty Eight essays are hailed as *Intellectual Exercise*. William Blake esteems them as *Good advice for Satan's Kingdom*. Many Bacons essays expose him as a philosopher cum politician. His some essays present him as an ardent lover and luscious fan of nature.

He has a strong belief that nature should be obeyed and not commanded. He advice everyone should understand the law of nature is a match stick. It helps us to light the lamp of mastery over nature. He desires a blazing revolution to emerge in Science, logic and Research. This alone will alone plant the society on the ladder of peace, plenty and prosperity. Mere research on simple or repeated themes is of no use and even foolish and meaningless. He complains that philosophy has been an unfertile field for ages. He welcomes new methods to make icons but he believes that they spent more time in theorizing and not in observation. He stresses that philosophy should be fed with new thoughts, new beliefs and new ideologies.

Idols as blind faith

Bacon proclaims that all medieval theories and arguments, suppositions and beliefs, thoughts and assumptions must be cast out. He shows ways to following the idols. The *idols of the mind* should mere images to shaken off. The den of one's own ideas and fancies, the *Idols of the cave*, ought to be flagged down. The *Idols of the tribe* which are the fallacies should be dispensed with. The errors that arise from the association of thoughts or men, the *Idols of the market place*, are to be red signaled. The final one is *the idols of the theatre* which are developed due to the deliberation of philosophers deserve to be rooted out. Bacon flashes the fact that these idols do keep us off the track of truth. His philosophy is that if we start with certainties we are sure to end in doubts and if we begin in doubts, we surely end in certainties.

Francis Bacon is a bright name in the history of English literature. Bacon was a man who was involved in the fields of knowledge such as literature, politics, philosophy, science, and other fields. This paper aims to attempts to bring the words of his will to life. His writings paved the way for the development of English prose and the development of the English language in the Fifteenth Century, when Latin was an official dialect on that period. He comments on all aspects of human life, from falling in love and talks about Atheism. It is true his advice is more of a folk weapon that paves the way for success in life than it is an ideal one. Therefore, it can be said that most of Bacon's advice is suitable for the majority of people.

Theory of forms

Bacon gets fame for his essays in world Literature era. The following years are 1597, 1612, 1625. They are scattered fragments of unrelated thoughts and piles narrow mind proverbs. Montagian was the forerunner of French essays. His essays are conversational, natural and have their own emotional tone. But Bacon essays are different from them. Their purposes are also different. The subtitle of his essays based on the social and Moral Advice. His essays embody a unified vision of worldliness and science, common sense and way to live. His collection of essays can be described as 'a guide to successes. His essays reveals with Greek and Roman substantiation, drawing conclusions based on his own expertise in the fields of natural science.

Each Essays like a shower of pearls, touches on different points, while simultaneously developing them and is constructed according to logical principles. Their specialty is due to the thoughts they have absorbed and the way in which knowledge has been embedded in those thoughts as a result of introspection. Idioms and Phrases are used like proverbs in everyday English. Some texts are to be tasted, some are to be swallowed, and some are to be digested. Reading makes a person to a complete person, Discussion makes a person be prepared, and Writing makes a perfect person. Bacon has stood in the line of his life and his writings. He said that everyone has not concerned with the mere tower of intelligence,

but they will create the plans for humanity benefit. He agrees with the all forms of studies and it has to be helpful for the enrichment of ideal life on the earth.

Explorer of Experimental research

Bacon's chief objective is that man should acquire knowledge which alone will increase his supremacy on earth. He wished to spread his wings of genius over scores of sciences. He did not endorse the theories the theories propounded by Copernicus and Kepler. He rejected Gilbert and even Harvey. This was why his books on science and philosophy were left in chaos and confusion at his death. Nowadays he is respected as the Originator of the modern school of experimental research. His first choice was Natural Science and he expressed himself as representative of Renaissance. *The Advancement of Learning* written in 1605 is his most celebrated work on philosophy. His other popular work, *Novum Organum* drafted in 1620, advocates a criticism of the past and a programme for the future.

He wants to insist everyone, walking along the road with distilled nature instead of trekking in the path of books and traditions. The natural history of countries and continents must be worked out together. This can be made possible by tapping the mechanism of induction. But, induction does not mean the details of information. It should have the gift of a streamlined system for classification of facts to find out the ultimate truth. To cite an example, Bacon desires to know what *heat* is. His perspiring intellectual efforts have convinced him to decide that heat is one form of motion. This innovation is his greatest contribution to Natural Sciences. His *Theory of Forms* is similar to Plato's *Theory of Ideas* and Aristotle's *Theory of Realities*. He means the forms are the set of rules and regulations. The form of heat means the law of heat. These laws do help in redefining and remaking things and held beliefs.

Writings of Exertion

Bacon has published a book in the English language in 1605. It concerns the basic ideas of 'Importance of Education'. He was able to explore all the science knowledge in his time. He seeks to explore to reach the truth and to classifying the different branches of knowledge. Moreover he wrote down his thoughts in Latin, which was poetic and authoritative language of that time. The '*New Instrument* (1610) book reveals the general truth of the individual facts. The *Idols of the heart*, was a reference to the evil habits of the mind that prevent people from knowing the truth and cause them to make mistakes. He believed that it was necessary to remove the puns and superstitions that had confused science and philosophy during the middle Ages, making them separated.

His *New Atlantis* was published posthumously in the year of 1627. The book is based on the work of Sir Thomas Moore's *Utopia*. It is a fantasy book about an idealized prosperous country. Bacon gives prominence to scientific achievements without emphasizing government and public institutions. He wants

to build research centre for scientist called *Solomon's House*. He believes that great and wonderful works can be done there for the benefit of humanity. In *Politics* Bacon is like a Machivellian. In science he was a great philosopher. He wanted the expertise that nature can overcome to be made available to humanity through science. In law he reached pinnacle. His essays taught the ways a single man could gain supremacy in social and political life. His essays are filled with wisdom that could not be imitated.

Conclusion

Bacon has an eminent place in the history of contemporary thought in literary circle. He is considered a pioneer of deductive method and an attempt to organize scientific procedures logically. He said that the new era flourishing the right principles of intense passion in research, patience in deciding and concluding something, and forgets the ancient period. He transferred the Golden Age from the mythical infancy to the future modern achievements. An eloquent voice of optimism, and he possesses the intellectual excellences that convinced the geniuses who could move the world. He was named as the Role model by the founders of the Royal society in 1662. The French intellectual wizards who compiled the *Encyclopedia* dedicated to Bacon. He was praised as the *Greatest, the most universal and the most eloquent of philosophers* by scholars. He paved the way to explain difficult meaning in few short words. There is no personal revelation in the essays of Bacon as it is traced in plenty in the essays of Lamb and Montague. Thus, Bacon never talks about himself but talks a lot about the world. He himself said that *he had all the knowledge in all*.

References:

- Abbott, Edwin A. Bacon, An Account of His Life and Works, 1885
- Bacon's Essays Edited by F.G. Selby. 1889, Macmillan.
- ----- Essays. RAMA BROTHERS INDIA PVT. LTD.
- ----- Essays. Lakshmi Narain Agarwal Educational Publishers, Agra-3.
- Crompton – Rickett Arthur:- A History of English Literature London, New york, Doge Pub company.
- Legouis Caza man's :- History of English Literature Shree pub.Jan -2011.
- Nair, Ramachandran. K. R. Essays on the History of English Literature. Chennai: Emerald Publishers, 2013. Print.

- Walker, Hugh. The English Essay and Essayists. 1915.